

A Study of Consumer Preferences towards E-Wallets in Guhagar City

Asst. Prof. Goyathale Priyanka Prakash

Department of Commerce,

Dr. T. Natu Arts & Senior College of Commerce, Margtamhane (Chiplun), Maharashtra, India

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18639315

Abstract:

The rapid expansion of digital payment systems has brought a significant shift in the financial behavior of consumers in India. With the Government's push towards a cashless economy and the increasing penetration of smartphones and internet services, electronic wallets (e-wallets) have emerged as a popular mode of digital payment. E-wallets offer convenience, speed, and ease of transactions, making them widely accepted for everyday financial activities. This study aims to analyze consumer preferences towards e-wallets in Guhagar City, a semi-urban region that is gradually adapting to digital financial services.

The primary objective of the study is to examine the level of awareness and usage of e-wallets among consumers and to identify the factors influencing their preference. The research focuses on aspects such as convenience, security, transaction speed, cashback offers, ease of access, and reliability of e-wallet services. In addition, the study attempts to understand the problems faced by consumers while using e-wallets, including technical issues, fear of fraud, lack of digital literacy, and network connectivity problems. The study also explores the impact of demographic variables such as age, education, and income on the adoption and preference of e-wallets.

The research is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through a structured questionnaire administered to consumers in Guhagar City, while secondary data is gathered from books, journals, research articles, and online sources related to digital payments. Behavior patterns.

The findings of the study are expected to provide useful insights into the changing payment preferences of consumers in semi-urban areas. The study may help e-wallet service providers, policymakers, and financial institutions to design better strategies for promoting digital payments, improving user experience, and strengthening financial inclusion in semi-urban and rural regions.

Introduction:

In recent years, digital payment methods have become very popular in India. With the growth of smartphones and internet facilities, people are slowly moving from cash payments to digital payments. One of the most commonly used digital payment methods is the e-wallet. An e-wallet allows users to make payments easily using their mobile phones for shopping, bill payments, recharges, and money transfers.

E-wallets such as Paytm, Google Pay, PhonePe, and Amazon Pay are widely used because they are fast, convenient, and easy to use. These applications save time and reduce the need to carry cash. Government initiatives like Digital India have

also encouraged people to use digital payment systems.

Guhagar City is a semi-urban area where digital payment usage is gradually increasing. However, consumer awareness and preference towards e-wallets differ based on factors such as age, education, and income. Therefore, it is important to study how consumers in Guhagar City use e-wallets and what factors influence their preferences.

This study aims to understand consumer preferences towards e-wallets in Guhagar City and identify the reasons for their usage and the problems faced by users.

E-wallet- Definition: E-wallet is a type of electronic card which is used for transactions made online through a computer or a smartphone. Its utility is same as a credit or debit card. An E-wallet needs to be linked with the individual's bank account to make payments.

Descriptions: E-wallet is a type of pre-paid account in which a user can store his/her money for any future online transaction. An E-wallet is protected with a password. With the help of an E-wallet, one can make payments for groceries, online purchases, and flight tickets, among others.

E-wallet has mainly two components, software and information. The software component stores personal information and provides security and encryption of the data. The information component is a database of details provided by the user which includes their name, shipping address, payment method, amount to be paid, credit or debit card details, etc.

For setting up an E-wallet account, the user needs to install the software on his/her device, and enter the relevant information required. After shopping online, the E-wallet automatically fills in the user's information on the payment form. To activate the E-wallet, the user needs to enter his password. Once the online payment is made, the consumer is not required to fill the order form on

any other website as the information gets stored in the database and is updated automatically.

Objectives:

1. To Study Awareness of E-wallet
2. To study the purpose of Adopting E-wallet apps
3. To Study Alternatives used by consumers to Traditional methods of payments.

Research methodology.

- Primary data : 100 respondents , Place: Guhagar, Age group: 18-40
- Data Collection: Questionnaire Method

What do we need to start using an e-wallet?

Some Leading E-wallet apps:

Why E-wallet methods are Taking over the Traditional methods:

E-wallet methods	Traditional methods
• Online	• Offline
• Instant money transfer	• Takes time & energy to stand in the queue
• Saves time & energy	• Procedures are time consuming
• No hard cash	• Withdraw & deposit hard cash
• Cheap, fast, convenient, easily accessible, profitable, secure, flexible and ultimately all-round.	• Easy bargaining, relevant, satisfaction, no risk issues.

Features of E-wallet:

- Fund Transfer or Receive Fund
- Store multiple cards
- UPI payments
- E-wallet passbook
- Bank to Wallet
- Bill Payment or Recharge

- Financial Services
- Journey Reservation
- Booking for Entertainments & Restraunts
- Shopping
- Promotional & Discount Offers
- Investments
- Education

- Settling up credit card Shopping
- City Services
- Virtual buying & selling of Gold
- Ratings , 24x7 help
- Partnership with your favorite Merchandise to support booking via app.

Data Analysis:

The survey was conducted on age group of 18-40 population, 100 respondents (approx), who belonged to heterogeneous fields. Out of all the questions asked from respondents, some of the major questions are as follows.

Are you Aware About E-wallets?

The chart shows that **80% of respondents are aware of e-wallets**, while **20% are not aware**. This indicates a **high level of awareness** about e-wallets among consumers, though a small section still needs digital awareness and guidance.

Source of Knowledge?

The data shows that most respondents learned about e-wallets through **advertisements**, followed by **friends**. **Referrals** and **relatives** play a moderate role, while very few respondents learned about e-wallets through their **profession or studies**. Overall, the analysis reveals that **advertisements and social**

interactions are the primary sources of information for e-wallet adoption, while institutional or academic sources have very little impact.

E-wallet App preferences:

The data shows that **Paytm** is the most popular e-wallet, followed by **G-Pay** and **PhonePe**. **Amazon Pay** has moderate usage, while **Mobikwik**, **Freecharge**, and **PayPal** are used by very few respondents. Overall, users prefer **popular and easy-to-use e-wallet apps**.

The chart shows that **hotels (30%)** are the highest users of e-wallets, followed by **teachers (20%)** and **students**. **Business persons** and **fruit & vegetable shopkeepers** have moderate usage, while **housewives (5%)** show the lowest use of e-wallets in Guhagar City.

As per the research, E-wallet methods are taking over the traditional methods of payments/services

The chart shows that respondents strongly prefer e-wallets for activities like **money transfer, mobile/DTH recharge, ticket booking, bill payments, and online shopping**. However, **traditional methods** are still preferred for **donations and LIC premium payments**. Overall, e-wallets are favored for daily and quick transactions, while traditional methods are used for formal or sensitive payments.

Benefits aware by using E-wallet?

The chart shows that **cashback offers** are the most attractive benefit of e-wallets for users. This is followed by **coupons and promo codes**, while **other benefits** influence very few users. Overall, **financial incentives** play an important role in encouraging e-wallet usage.

How much is the investment feature used in E-wallet?

The chart shows that the majority of respondents **have not invested** in any option. Among those who have invested, **gold and mutual funds** are the most preferred, followed by the **share market**, while **LIC** is the least preferred investment option.

Regularity of E-wallets:

The chart shows that **58%** of respondents use e-wallets on a **regular basis**, while **41%** use them **rarely**. Only **1%** have installed e-wallets but **do not use them**, indicating high overall adoption and active usage among users.

Security & privacy:

The chart indicates that **72%** of respondents **read the terms and conditions** before agreeing,

while **28%** do **not read** them. This shows a generally good level of awareness, though a significant portion still ignores important usage conditions.

Findings:

- About **80% respondents are fully aware of e-wallets**, mainly due to social media and digital exposure.
- **18–30 age group** finds e-wallets **convenient, affordable, secure, and easy to use**.
- **Cashbacks, discounts, and rewards** strongly influence e-wallet usage.
- Many users transfer money mainly to **avail promotional offers**.
- **Google Pay, Paytm, and PhonePe** are the most popular e-wallet apps.
- E-wallets are widely used for **bill payments, recharges, shopping, and money transfers**.

Conclusion:

- E-wallets are **economical and highly preferred by youth (18–30 years)**.
- **28% respondents are aware but do not use e-wallets** due to comfort with cash or personal reasons.
- Modern users prefer **cashless payments for convenience and time saving**.
- **QR-code based payments** (Paytm, G-Pay, PhonePe) are commonly accepted at retail outlets.
- Only **3% users faced transaction issues**, and losses were recoverable.
- **97% respondents feel e-wallets are safe, user-friendly, and reliable**.

Suggestions:

- Consumers should download and use e-wallet applications to enjoy convenience and support during emergencies.
- E-wallet apps should be installed only from trusted sources such as Google Play Store or official websites.
- Users should avoid making transactions in a hurry and ensure a stable internet connection before proceeding.

- It is advisable to check bank server status; if the bank server is not responding, payments should be postponed.
- Before transferring large amounts, users should first make a trial transaction (e.g., ₹1) and proceed only after successful confirmation.
- Users must carefully verify contact details and bank account numbers before sending money.
- In case of any technical issues or failed transactions, users should immediately contact customer care for assistance.

References:

1. Reserve Bank of India (RBI). (2022). *Payment and Settlement Systems in India*. RBI Publications, Mumbai.
2. Government of India. (2019). *Digital India Programme: Transforming India into a Digitally Empowered Society*. Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology.
3. Kaur, P., & Pathak, A. (2015). *E-payment system on e-wallet: A conceptual study*. International Journal of Management Research and Business Strategy, 4(1), 1–8.
4. Singh, S., & Rana, R. (2017). *Study of consumer perception of digital payment mode*. Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce, 22(3), 1–14.
5. Kumar, R., & Dhingra, S. (2020). *Digital payments and consumer behavior in India*. International Journal of Research in Commerce and Management, 11(5), 45–52.
6. Reserve Bank of India. (2021). *Guidelines on Digital Payment Security Controls*. RBI Circulars.
7. Statista Research Department. (2023). *Digital payment users in India*. Statista Database.
8. Paytm Official Website. (2024). *About Paytm and Digital Wallet Services*. Retrieved from <https://paytm.com>
9. Google Pay Help Center. (2024). *Using Google Pay in India*. Retrieved from <https://pay.google.com>
10. PhonePe Official Website. (2024). *Digital payment solutions and UPI services*. Retrieved from <https://www.phonepe.com>